

4B_1b FDP reference implementation

📌 Introduction

Running a FAIR Data Point to expose your metadata is an option if you have the necessary resources/capacity and knowledge. We also recommend setting up an [automatic export](#) as the preferred method for exposing your metadata.

Requirements:

- a (virtual) machine,
- installed [Docker](#)

🧠 Explanation / Approach

The FAIR Data Point (FDP) reference implementation is available as a Docker Compose distribution. You can find detailed instructions in the official documentation at [About FAIR Data Point — FAIR Data Point documentation](#).

📘 Users are advised to use to version [1.7.4 of the FDP server](#) and [1.17.1 of the FDP client](#) to make full use of all functionalities with v2 of the metadata.

There are two options to deploy the FDP reference implementation:

- **Local deployment:** For a simple setup, the [Local Deployment](#) is a good place to start.
- **Production deployment:** If you plan to use the FDP in a real production environment, there's also a [Production Deployment](#) option available.

📘 Here is an example of the implementation done at AUMC of a FDP myDRE environment [AUMC - FDP implementation in myDRE environment](#) . Radboudumc followed [this](#) tutorial in Azure.

⚖️ Pros / Cons

Pros

- All components (FDP client, FDP server, blazegraph) deployed in one go.

Cons

- Requires knowledge on deploying docker containers,maintenance of the server and application

✔ Next steps

If you have an FDP and compliant metadata ([4B Exposing metadata](#)) you can now enter the metadata into your FDP [4B_2 Metadata entry into an FDP](#) .